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Variety	Frequency distribution of yield in t/ha						Mean yield (t/ha)
	<1.0	<1.5	<2.0	<2.5	<3.0	>3.0	
CR231-1	1	3	3	0	2	1	1.9
Dular	2	1	1	2	2	1	2.1
IET7255	2	2	2	0	2	1	1.8
IET7259	2	1	2	2	0	2	2.0
IR50	1	1	5	0	0	2	1.8
IR9209-47-1-1-6-2	2	1	3	2	0	1	1.7
IR9729-67-3	2	0	2	2	1	2	2.2
IR9708-51-1-2	1	3	1	4	0	0	1.8
IR8608-189-2-2-1-3	2	1	3	1	1	1	1.7
IR13204-24-1-6	1	3	2	2	1	0	1.7
Kiran	1	3	2	1	0	2	2.1
Panke	1	1	5	0	0	2	2.0
Suweon 287	1	2	3	1	1	1	1.8
Mean							2.0
CD at 5%							0.2

reproductive phases. Panke, an indigenous genotype, yielded an average 1.9 t/ha (see table).

In 1983, the environmental conditions were more favorable. BG367-7 yielded highest, 2.5 t/ha followed by BKNLR-75091 and BG367-4 (see table). Of the varieties tested, Panke, Kiran, and IET7259 had the most stable yields. □

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization HYBRID RICE

Evaluation of F₁ hybrids on the Cuu Long Delta, Vietnam

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We evaluated six F₁ hybrids developed at CLRRI in 1984 dry season in a randomized block design with three replications. There were eight 4-m-long rows per plot. Plants were transplanted at 20 × 15-cm spacing, and received 75-26-25 kg NPK/ha.

The F₁ hybrids had negative heterobeltiosis in plant height, panicles/m²,

Table 2. Performance of F₁ hybrids in Oman, Hau Giang, Vietnam, 1984 dry season.

Hybrid and check varieties	Duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Pan/m ²	Grains /pan	Sterility (%)	1000-g wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)
V20A/NN3A (IR36)	93	69	265	76	20.3	31	4.0
Zhen Shan 97 A /NN3A	93	78	263	86	23.2	28	4.9
NN3A	105	90	412	101	17.9	23	5.6
V20A/NN4B (IR42)	97	83	276	77	19.6	30	6.5
Zhen Shan 97 A /NN4B	97	76	277	121	11.5	27	5.6
NN4B	135	86	375	107	16.6	22	4.8
V20A/IR54	95	75	299	79	20.9	31	2.5
Zhen Shan 97 A /IR54	95	76	291	89	22.8	29	2.9
IR54	122	91	361	112	15.8	26	6.0
V20B	97	71	284	74	16.5	30	2.3
97B	103	74	269	97	26.1	28	2.8
CV%		9	17	14	24		15
LSD 5%		10	72	19	6.6		1.1

Table 1. Standard heterosis and heterobeltiosis in yield of F₁ hybrids, Omon, Vietnam, 1984.

Hybrid	Standard heterosis (compared with NN3A)	Heterobeltiosis
V20A/NN4B	+16.45	+33.19
Zhen Shan 97A/NN4B	+0.54	+17.57
Zhen Shan 97A/NN3A	-12.53	-12.53
V20A/NN3A	-33.39	-33.39
Zhen Shan 97A/IR54	-51.75	-51.99
V20A/IR54	-55.81	-58.97

grains/panicle, and sterility and positive heterobeltiosis in 1,000-grain weight (Table 1).

Only V20A/NN4B and Zhen Shan 97A/NN4B performed better than the best parents. They yielded 6.5 and 5.6 t/ha (Table 2). These hybrids had positive standard yield heterosis and heterobeltiosis (Table 1) compared with commercial NN3A. V20A/NN4B and Zhen Shan 97A/NN4B yielded 46% more. Other hybrids did not yield well. Generally, the F₁ hybrids yielded poorly because of a genetic defect in cytoplasmic male

sterile (cms) lines used.

NN4B was a better restorer than NN3A and IR54 for the cms lines V20A and Zhen Shan 97A in Vietnam. □

Harvest index and straw weight of some experimental F₁ rice hybrids

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Crop grain yield is the product of harvest index (HI) and total dry matter. Theore-

Table 1. Grain weight, straw weight, and HI of F₁ hybrids and check varieties, IRRI.^a

Variety and F ₁ hybrid	Grain weight (g/plant)	Straw weight (g/plant)	HI
<i>Experiment 1</i>			
IR36	33.6 ab	23.3	bcde 0.590 ab
IR50	32.4 abc	20.9 def	0.608 a
IR56	31.6 abc	23.7 abcd	0.571 bc
IR58	34.4 a	22.0 cdef	0.609 a
IR60	28.2 c	21.0 def	0.573 bc
IR29708-41-2-2-3	34.7 a	25.6 ab	0.575 bc
Average	32.5	22.8	0.588
IR747B2-6-3A/IR50	35.1 a	26.3 a	0.572 bc
V20A/IR2307-247-2-2-3	27.9 c	19.2 f	0.593 ab
IR46828A/Suweon 294	29.1 bc	20.6 ef	0.583 ab
IR19799A/IR13429-6-3-3-1	30.5 abc	24.8 abc	0.551 c
V20A/IR13420-6-3-3-1	32.0 abc	24.5 abc	0.564 bc
Average	30.9	23.1	0.572
<i>Experiment 2</i>			
IR36	34.9 ab	22.6 cd	0.606 ab
IR50	33.4 abc	22.5 cd	0.597 abc
IR56	30.6 cd	22.8 cd	0.574 cde
IR58	32.9 bcd	21.2 d	0.608 a
IR60	32.7 bcd	23.5 bcd	0.582 cde
IR29708-41-2-2-3	34.7 ab	26.5 a	0.568 de
Average	33.2	23.2	0.589
MR365A/IR13524-21-2-3-3-2-2	36.4 a	25.9 ab	0.585 bcde
MR365A/Milyang 46	32.5 bcd	22.8 cd	0.588 abcd
IR46826A/IR15795-232-3-3-3-2	35.7 ab	30.2	0.542 f
MR365A/Milyang 57	33.1 abcd	24.6 abc	0.573 de
MR365A/Suweon 287	29.9 d	23.1 cd	0.563 ef
Average	33.5	25.3	0.570
<i>Experiment 3^b</i>			
IR36	32.5 abc	21.2 e	0.605 ab
IR50	35.1 a	22.0 e	0.614 a
IR56	32.7 abc	24.4 de	0.572 d
IR58	33.0 abc	21.6 e	0.604 ab
IR60	34.5 ab	23.8 de	0.592 abcd
IR29708-41-2-2-3	33.6 ab	23.5 de	0.588 bcd
Average	33.6	22.8	0.596
IR46828A/IR13524-21-2-3-3-2-2	36.3 a	24.4 de	0.598 abc
IR19799A/IR2797-125-3-2-2	33.0 abc	23.4 de	0.586 bcd
V20A/IR54	26.5 d	13.7	0.659
IR46826A/IR13419-113-1	27.6 cd	28.4 cd	0.493 fg
IR46828A/IR54	35.8 a	26.5 de	0.574 cd
IR46828A/IR10781-143-2-3	34.5 ab	25.7 de	0.572 d
Average	32.3	23.7	0.580
IR42	33.9 ab	36.1 ab	0.484
IR29723-143-3-2-1	34.5 ab	37.9 a	0.477
IR24588-34-2-2-3-3	29.2 bcd	27.8 cd	0.512 efg
IR28150-84-3-3-2	34.3 ab	31.7 bc	0.520 e
Average	33.0	33.4	0.498

^a In a column in each experiment, figures with a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level. ^b In experiment 3, IR42, IR29723-143-3-2-1, IR24588-34-2-2-3-3, and IR28150-84-3-3-2 are late maturing. The other varieties and F₁ hybrids are early maturing.

Table 2. Relations among grain weight, straw weight, and HI, IRRI.

Correlation between	Correlation coefficient ^a										
	Experiment 1			Experiment 2			Experiment 3			Check	F ₁
	Check	F ₁	Check and F ₁	Check	F ₁	Check and F ₁	Check	F ₁	Check and F ₁		
Grain weight and straw weight	0.565 ^{ns}	0.903*	0.694*	0.377 ^{ns}	0.740 ^{ns}	0.599 ^{ns}	0.106 ^{ns} (0.149 ^{ns})	0.481 ^{ns}	0.413 ^{ns} (0.321 ^{ns})	0.406 ^{ns} (0.240 ^{ns})	0.634**
Grain weight and HI	0.433 ^{ns}	-0.456 ^{ns}	0.156 ^{ns}	0.270 ^{ns}	-0.062 ^{ns}	0.018 ^{ns}	0.387 ^{ns} (0.124 ^{ns})	-0.010 ^{ns}	-0.062 ^{ns} (0.002 ^{ns})	0.391 ^{ns} (0.096 ^{ns})	-0.065 ^{ns}
Straw weight and HI	-0.497 ^{ns}	-0.792 ^{ns}	-0.601 ^{ns}	-0.789 ^{ns}	-0.715 ^{ns}	-0.788**	-0.875* (-0.961**)	4.881*	-0.881** (-0.934**)	-0.680** (-0.940**)	-0.809**

^a Correlation coefficient in parentheses includes the late maturing varieties. ** = significant at 1% level, * = significant at 5% level, ns = not significant.

tically, high yield is achieved by increasing HI, total dry matter, or both.

The goal of hybrid rice breeding is to get an F₁ hybrid with HI and total dry matter higher than those of pureline varieties (checks). We compared HI and total dry matter production (grain plus straw weights) of some IRRI experimental F₁ hybrids with those of pureline varieties.

In 1984 dry season, 3 experiments were conducted in 2- × 5.8-m plots in a randomized complete block design with 4 replications. At harvest, 1-m² plots were sampled.

F₁ hybrids had high grain weight in each experiment (Table 1), but they did not significantly outperform all the checks. In experiment 1, IR747-B2-6-3A/IR50 grain weight was highest but only significantly higher than that of IR60. In experiment 2, MR365A/IR13524-21-2-3-3-2-2 yielded significantly more than IR56, IR58, and IR60. In experiment 3, IR46828A/IR13524-21-2-3-3-2-2 grain weight was highest but only significantly higher than IR24588-34-2-2-3-3.

The increased grain weight was associated with increased straw weight (Table 1). HI of F₁ hybrids with high grain weight was the same as or slightly lower than that of the checks, indicating that high dry matter production was responsible for high grain yield.

Grain weight did not correlate with HI (Table 2). Straw weight positively correlated with grain weight, especially for the F₁ hybrids. There was a negative correlation between straw weight and HI.

Although F₁ hybrids included in this study accumulated more dry matter, they tended to have lower HI than pureline varieties do. This explains why their grain weight was not significantly higher than

that of the checks. The results of the present experiment suggest that improvement of parental lines is needed for F₁ hybrids to show further superiority over checks. □

Yield depression in F₂ hybrids of rice *Oryza sativa* L.

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We evaluated four F₂ rice hybrids and their corresponding F₁ parents with IR54, a recommended pureline variety, as check in a replicated yield trial in 1983 dry season at IRRI. Twenty-one-day-old seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing and one seedling per hill, in 5.0- × 3.4-m plots, NPK was applied at 120-50-30 kg/ha.

The F₁ hybrids and IR54 flowered relatively earlier and were more uniform in flowering and plant height than the F₂.

Yield and yield depression in F₂ rice hybrids and the corresponding F₁ hybrids.

Hybrid, check	Yield (t/ha)		Yield depression ^a (%) in F ₂
	F ₁ hybrid	F ₂ hybrid	
IET3257/IR2797-105-2-2-3	8.3	6.6	-21**
IET3257/IR54	8.3	6.8	-19**
IR11248-242-3-2/IR15324-117-3-2	7.7	6.6	-14**
IR1124&242-3-2/IR19672-19-3-3-1	8.2	6.8	-18**
IR54 (check)	6.7		

^a ** = significant at 1% level.

Flowering took about 15 d between 99 and 114 d after sowing in IET3257/IR2797 and 12 d for the 3 other F₂ hybrids. Uneven F₂ plant height, flowering, and maturity were due to segregation of genes for those traits.

Grain yield was determined from 5 m². Because of staggered F₂ maturity, plants were harvested on two dates. Grain yield was adjusted to 14% moisture, and reported in t/ha. Yield depression in F₂ was computed as (F₂ - F₁) ÷ F₁ and expressed as a percentage. Statistical significance of the difference was tested using LSD.

Yield depression (see table) in F₂ ranged from 14 to 21% and was significant in all the hybrids. However, the F₂ yields were comparable with those of IR54. The highest yield depression in F₂ was observed in the combination IET3257/IR2797. The same combination had also expressed the highest yield heterosis in F₁. Therefore, to exploit the yield advantage of F₁ rice hybrids, it would be necessary to sow fresh F₁ seed every year. Sowing F₂ seed (harvest made from F₁ rice hybrid) would significantly reduce yield. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization TISSUE CULTURE

Response of rice anthers to callus induction and plant regeneration

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Anther culture can speed genetic improvement of crops by increasing selection efficiency within a short time. We studied the response of anthers to culture medium.

Cold shocked anthers of 40 boro varieties, breeding lines, and F₂ plants were cultured in N6 (for japonica) and modified H5 and SK-8 (for indica and indica/japonica) media at early to mid-uninucleate stage of microspore development. Of the 18 lines that produced calli, 2 were japonicas, 1 was indica/japonica, and 15 were indicas. Anther

Rice anther variability in inducing callus and plant differentiation, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Variety or line	Type	Anthers inoculated (no.)	Induction		Differentiation ^a (%)		
			No.	%	Roots only	Albino plants	Green plants
Zhing hua-2	japonica	270	60	22	50	18	0
Zhing hua-5	japonica	600	222	37	30	37	25
BG96-3/J2	indica	311	23	7	33	33	17
BR161-2B-58	indica	262	6	2	60	0	0
Guichao No. 2	indica	368	2	0	100	0	0
Habiganj Boro-VI	indica	155	39	25	50	30	0
Habiganj Boro VIII	indica	162	56	35	45	10	0
IR40	indica	330	11	3	57	14	0
IR19660-11	indica	215	3	1	33	0	0
IR19660-311	indica	404	68	13	70	15	5
IR19090-24-5-3-1-1	indica	230	1	0	100	0	0
Pajam	indica/japonica	1825	82	4	48	27	11
Zenith	indica	230	3	1	67	0	0
BR4228 (F ₂)	indica	840	54	6	37	35	10
BR4229 (F ₂)	indica	295	8	3	60	40	0
BR4249 (F ₂)	indica	480	15	3	50	20	0
BR4251 (F ₂)	indica	455	3	1	100	0	0
BR4252 (F ₂)	indica	575	12	2	50	20	0
Total (induction)		8007	668	8.34	-	-	-
Weighted av (differentiation) ^a		-	-	-	48.3	23.1	7.7

^a Based on number of calli transferred for differentiation.